

CMIP6 Publication Closure

Matthew Mizielinski (MOHC), Paul Durack (LLNL), Sasha Ames (LLNL), Philip Kershaw (STFC), Beth Dingley (CMIP-IPO), Eleanor O'Rourke (CMIP-IPO)

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The CMIP6 ESGF project is to be closed to new submissions. This change does not affect CMIP6Plus or any other ESGF project.

We are anticipating CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track data publication to commence in late 2025¹. In preparation for CMIP7 and to redirect scarce resources to serve CMIP7 needs, we have decided to close the ESGF CMIP6 project to further publications on Monday 7th April 2025. This will enable the limited ESGF and CMIP resources to be redirected to developing the next-generation infrastructure to support CMIP7 activities.

The currently active CMIP6Plus, obs4MIPs, input4MIPs and other small projects will not be affected by the CMIP6 closure. New publications to these projects will remain active until CMIP7 infrastructure is tested and established, with migration of these ongoing projects from old to new infrastructure in planning. We will consult with CMIP6Plus registered MIPs actively publishing to the project before deciding on a timeline for project closure.

Modelling groups can publish further CMIP6 DECK like experiments into CMIP6Plus providing they follow the guidance² and use the updated CVs and MIP tables linked from the guidance. MIPs who need to publish data before CMIP7 Assessment Fast Track delivery begins should contact the CMIP International Project Office to discuss whether adding to CMIP6Plus is possible.

All CMIP6 data will remain available for the foreseeable future and the ESGF and CMIP communities are working hard to ensure that in addition high demand datasets access is maintained.

¹ <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-phases/cmip7/#fast-track>

² <https://wcrp-cmip.org/cmip-phases/cmip6plus/>